

A Formal Total Synthesis of (\pm)-Enterolactone[†]

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A radical cyclization based methodology has been applied for the formal total synthesis of (\pm)-enterolactone (1), the first lignan isolated from human source. Bromoacetalization reaction of the cinnamyl alcohols 7 and 13 using ethyl vinyl ether and NBS, generated the bromoacetals 8 and 15. The 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization reaction of the bromoacetals 8 and 15 with *in situ* generated catalytic tri-n-butyltin hydride and AIBN furnished a 3 : 2 diastereomeric mixture of the cyclic acetals 9 and 16. Sonochemically accelerated Jones oxidation of the cyclic acetals 9 and 16 yielded the γ -butyrolactones 10 and 12 completing the formal total synthesis of (\pm)-enterolactone. Alternatively radical cyclization of the bromoacetate 17 furnished a 1 : 2 mixture of the lactone 10 and the reduced product 18.

Lignans of many types, isolated from plants, have been found to exhibit a variety of biological activities, such as cytotoxic, fungitoxic, and growth inhibitory activity, and are used for the development of chemotherapeutic agents¹. Consequently, lignans have received a great deal of attention from synthetic chemists. In 1980, Stich *et al.*² isolated a new compound, enterolactone, from the phenolic extracts of urine from pregnant women, which they originally thought as a phenolic steroid, but careful spectroscopic analysis led to the elucidation of its structure as *trans*-3,4-bis[3-hydroxyphenyl)methyl]dihydro-2-(3*H*)-furanone (1). Simultaneously, Setchell *et al.*³ reported the isolation of enterolactone 1 along with enterodiol 2, in other mammals, rats, and vervet monkeys. It was the first time, lignans were isolated from human origin, hitherto, lignans known to originate only from plants. It is interesting to note that the enterolactone 1 isolated from natural sources has only an optical purity of <10%. Unlike all the previously known natural lignans, the two mammalian lignans 1 and 2 lacks

1 (enterolactone)

2 (enterodiol)

oxygen functionality at 4'- and 4''-positions and carry the phenolic hydroxy groups only at the 3'- and 3''-positions of the aromatic rings. The significant biological activities, such

as cytotoxic, cardiotoxic, immunosuppressant etc., of enterolactone 1 has generated an intense interest in the synthesis of enterolactone 1 and several approaches⁴ employing various general methods known in lignan chemistry have been reported.

(eqn 1)

Last decade has witnessed a rapid growth in the use of free radical reactions for carbon-carbon bond formation, particularly the intramolecular version leading to cyclic compounds, now commonly referred to as radical cyclization reactions (eqn.1), and synthesis of a variety of carbonyl and heterocyclic systems were achieved⁵. Application of radical cyclization reactions in the synthesis of a variety of butyrolactones is well-documented. However, synthesis of lignan lactones via radical cyclization reactions were not reported. Only recently, reports appeared in the literature on the application of radical cyclization reactions for the synthesis of tetrahydrofuran⁶ and furofuran⁷ lignans. Based on the bromoacetal cyclization originally developed by Stork *et al.*⁸, synthesis of a variety of butyrolactones, both simple as well as spiro fused, were achieved in our laboratory⁹. With this background, a radical cyclization reaction based methodology was developed for the synthesis of enterolactone 1¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Retrosynthetic analysis of enterolactone 1 based on the radical cyclization methodology is depicted in Scheme 1 with the cinnamyl alcohol 3 as the starting material. A bromoacetalization reaction converts the cinnamyl alcohol into the radical precursor 4. The 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization reaction of the bromoacetal 4, generates the cyclic acetal 5 which on hydrolysis and oxidation generates the butyrolactone 6. Kinetic alkylation of 6 generates enterolactone.

[†]Respectfully dedicated to Professor T. R. Govindachari.

Scheme 1

First the sequence was carried out with the phenolic hydroxy group protected as its methyl ether. The required starting material 3-methoxycinnamyl alcohol **7** was prepared from 3-methoxybenzaldehyde via a Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction followed by regioselective lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the resulting cinnamate. A bromoacetalization reaction¹¹ was employed for the conversion of the cinnamyl alcohol **7** into the radical precursor **8**, and *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) was chosen as the source of Br⁺. Thus, addition of NBS to a methylene chloride solution of the allyl alcohol **7** and an excess of ethyl vinyl ether at -78° over a period of 1.5 h furnished the bromoacetal **8**, in 65% yield. The ¹H nmr spectrum exhibited a triplet at δ 4.77 due to acetal methine proton, a doublet at δ 3.42 due to bromomethylene group and a triplet at δ 1.25 due to methyl of ethoxy group in addition to other expected resonances, confirming the structure of the bromoacetal **8**. The key 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization reaction of the bromoacetal **8** was carried out employing an *in situ* generated catalytic tri-*n*-butyltin hydride in the presence of a catalytic amount of a radical initiator in *t*-butanol¹². Thus, refluxing a 0.2 M solution of the bromoacetal **8** in butanol with 0.15 equivalents of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride, 3 equivalents of sodium cyanoborohydride, and a catalytic amount of AIBN furnished a 3 : 2 diastereomeric mixture of the 5-*exo*-trig cyclized product, the cyclic acetal **9**, in 65% yield, whose structure was established from its spectral data, in particular the ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (see experimental section). For the conversion of the cyclic acetal **9** into the corresponding β-arylmethyl-γ-butyrolactone

10, a sonochemically accelerated one-pot procedure for the hydrolysis and oxidation using Jones reagent, was employed⁹. Thus, irradiation of an acetone solution of the acetal **9** with a freshly prepared 1.6 M Jones reagent in an ultrasonic bath for 5 min generated the γ-butyrolactone **10**, in 74% yield. The appearance of a carbonyl absorption band at 1770 cm⁻¹ due to a γ-lactone, and the disappearance of resonances due to acetal methine and ethoxy groups in the ¹H nmr spectrum confirmed the formation of lactone. Further, in the ¹H nmr spectrum, appearance of a triplet at δ 7.24 due to H-5', multiplet at 6.7–6.9 due to H-4' and H-6', a broad singlet at 6.69 due to H-2' aromatic protons, doublets of an AB quartet at 4.34 and 4.04 due to the methylene attached to oxygen, a singlet at 3.8 due to arylmethoxy group, a septet at 2.83 due to β-methine group, doublets of an AB quartet at 2.33 and 2.29 due to the methylene group attached to carbonyl group, and in the ¹³C nmr spectrum appearance of carbon resonance at 176.7 due to lactone carbonyl, at 159.7 due to the carbon bearing the methoxy group, 139.7, 129.6, 120.8, 114.4 and 111.7 due to rest of the aromatic carbons, at 72.5 due to the carbon attached to oxygen, at 55.0 due to aryl methoxy carbon and at 38.7, 36.8 and 34.0 ppm due to α,β and benzylic carbons confirmed the structure of the γ-lactone **10**. Final confirmation of the structure of the lactone **10** was achieved by comparison of the ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data with that reported in the literature^{4n,9,13}. Since the lactone has already been converted into enterolactone **1** via stereoselective alkylation (LDA/3-methoxybenzyl bromide) followed by demethylation (BBr₃)^{4n,p}, our synthesis of the butyrolactone **10** constitutes

a formal total synthesis of enterolactone.

Since the overall yield of the butyrolactone 10, from the cinnamyl alcohol 7 was less than that anticipated, the sequence was also carried out with the phenolic hydroxy group protected as its benzyl ether. The requisite starting material, 3-benzyloxybenzaldehyde (11) was prepared via benzylation of 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde employing a phase-transfer catalyst. The benzaldehyde 11 was converted into the γ -butyrolactone 12 employing the same methodology via the 3-benzyloxycinnamyl alcohol 13. Thus, Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction of the aldehyde 11 with triethyl phosphonoacetate in dry THF using sodium hydride as base furnished the cinnamate 14 in 82% yield, which on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride in ether at low temperature generated the cinnamyl alcohol 13, in 73% yield. Slow addition of NBS to a methylene chloride solution of the alcohol 13 and an excess of ethyl vinyl ether at -78° furnished the bromoacetal 15, in 80% yield. The 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization reaction of the bromoacetal 15 was

reaction of the bromoacetate 17 using *in situ* generated tri-*n*-butyltin hydride (0.15 equiv. of $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ and 2 equiv. of NaCNBH_3), however, generated only a mixture of the reduced product 18 (60%) and the cyclized product 10 (15%) which was separated by silica gel column chromatography. In an attempt to improve, the reaction was carried out with stoichiometric amount of tri-*n*-butyltin hydride. Thus, slow addition of a benzene solution of tri-*n*-butyltin hydride (1.5 equiv.) and AIBN (catalytic) to a refluxing solution of the bromoacetate 17 in benzene (overall concentration 0.005 M) over a period of 1 h furnished a 1 : 2 mixture of the cyclized product 10 and the reduced product 18, in 90% yield.

To summarize, a formal total synthesis of (\pm) enterolactone 1, the first lignan isolated from the human source has been achieved starting from *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde and also from *m*-benzyloxybenzaldehyde using a 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization reaction of either a bromoacetal or a bromoacetate as the key step.

carried out using *in situ* generated catalytic tri-*n*-butyltin hydride ($^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ and NaCNBH_3) in refluxing *t*-butanol in the presence of a catalytic amount of AIBN to furnish a 3 : 2 diastereomeric mixture of the cyclic acetal 16, in 64% yield. Finally, sonochemically accelerated reaction of the acetal 16 with a freshly prepared 1.6 M Jones reagent in acetone furnished the butyrolactone 12 in 74% yield, whose structure rests secured from its spectral data, in particular the ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra in comparison with those of the lactone 10. The conversion of the lactone 12 into enterolactone has already been reported^{4a}.

In an alternative methodology, instead of the bromoacetal 4, radical cyclization reaction of the corresponding bromoacetate¹⁴ for the generation of the lactone 10 was attempted. Thus, reaction of the cinnamyl alcohol 7 with bromoacetyl bromide in pyridine generated the bromoacetate 17, in 85% yield. The 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, ^1H (90, 200 and 270 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr spectra on Jeol FX-90Q, Bruker ACF-200 and WH-270 spectrometers, and low and high resolution mass measurements on a Jeol JMS-DX 303 GC-MS instrument using a direct inlet mode. Acme's silica gel G and silica gel (100–200 mesh) were used for analytical TLC and column chromatography respectively. CH_2Cl_2 was distilled from P_2O_5 . NBS, ethyl vinyl ether, sodium cyanoborohydride, tri-*n*-butyltin hydride, and tri-*n*-butyltin chloride (Fluka) were used without further purification. AIBN was recrystallized from methanol and stored in dark. Jones reagent was prepared according to the procedure reported in Vogel's text book.

4-[(3-Methoxyphenyl)methyl]dihydrofuran-2(3H)-one (10):

Bromoacetal 8: To a cold (-78°), magnetically stirred

solution of the cinnamyl alcohol **7** (1 g, 6 mmol) and ethyl vinyl ether (3 ml, 2.26 g, 31.3 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (10 ml) was added dropwise, a solution of NBS (1.3 g, 7.3 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (10 ml) over a period of 15 min. The reaction mixture was stirred and allowed to warm up to room temperature over a period of 2 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with ether (25 ml), washed with 0.5 *N* aq. NaOH followed by water and brine, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the residue on a silica gel (20 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the bromoacetal **8** (125 g, 65%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 1580, 1560, 1240, 1140, 1100, 1020, 750, 660 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.24 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, H-5'), 6.98 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, H-6'), 6.93 (1H, br s, H-2'), 6.82 (1H, dd, *J* 6 and 1.5 Hz, H-4'), 6.62 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz, Ar-CH=CH), 6.28 (1H, t of d, *J* 15.9 and 6.2 Hz, Ar-CH=CH CH_2), 4.77 (1H, t, *J* 5.5 Hz, O-CH-OEt), 4.29 (2H, dd, *J* 15 and 6.2 Hz, O- CH_2 -C=), 3.66 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 3.4-3.8 (2H, m, O- CH_2CH_3), 3.42 (2H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, CH_2Br), 1.25 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, OCH_2CH_3).

Hemiacetal 9 : To a solution of the bromoacetal **8** (1 g, 3.17 mmol) in *t*-BuOH (10 ml) were added $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.21 ml, 0.7 mmol), NaCHBH_3 (0.59 g, 9.5 mmol) and a catalytic amount of AIBN, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was taken in water (25 ml) and extracted with ether (3 \times 25 ml). The ether extract was washed with 1% aq. ammonia (10 ml) followed by brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the residue on a silica gel (5 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 4) as eluent furnished the cyclized product **9** (=3 : 2 mixture of ethoxy epimers, 0.55 g, 73.5%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 1600, 1585, 1260, 1150, 1110, 1050, 770, 690 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (270 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.20 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 6.70-6.85 (3H, m), 5.1-5.2 (1H, m, O-CH-OEt), 3.35-4.1 (4H, m, O- CH_2 and O- CH_2CH_3), 3.8 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.6-2.9 (2H, m, Ar- CH_2), 2.5 (1H, m), 2.2 (1H, ddd, *J* 14.5, 9.1 and 5.6 Hz), 2.06 (dd, *J* 14 and 7 Hz) and 1.5-1.8, (m) (2H), 1.22 and 1.18 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, O- CH_2CH_3); ^{13}C nmr (50 MHz, CDCl_3 , 3 : 2 mixture of diastereomers, DEPT) δ 159.7 (C, C-3'), 142.5 and 142.2 (C, C-1'), 129.4 (CH, C-5'), 121.1 and 121.0 (CH, C-2'), 114.5 (CH, C-4'), 111.4 and 111.3 (C, C-6'), 104.4 and 104.0 (CH, O-CH-O), 71.7 (CH_2 , $\text{CHC H}_2\text{-O}$), 63.0 and 62.6 (CH_2 , O- $\text{C H}_2\text{CH}_3$), 55.0 (CH_3 , Ar- OCH_3), 40.0 (CH, Ar- CH_2CH), 39.4 and 39.1 (CH_2 , $\text{CH}_2\text{CH-OEt}$), 38.8 (CH_2 , Ar- CH_2CH), 15.4 and 15.2 ppm (CH_3 , O- CH_2CH_3); *m/z* 236 (M^+), 190, 173, 131, 115, 91; HRMS : for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$, Found : 236.1411 (Calcd : 236.1412).

Lactone 10 : To a solution of the acetal **9** (0.235 g, 1 mmol) in acetone (1 ml), was added a freshly prepared 1.6

M Jones reagent (1 ml, 1.6 mmol) and the reaction mixture was sonicated in an ultrasonic cleaning bath for 5 min. A few drops of 2-propanol was added to the reaction mixture to consume the excess reagent, then diluted with ether (20 ml), washed with saturated aq. NaHCO_3 followed by brine, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the residue on a silica gel (5 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the lactone^{4n,9} **10** (0.15 g, 79%) : ν_{max} (neat) : 1770 (γ -lactone C=O), 1600, 1595, 1260, 1170, 1050, 785, 695 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (270 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.24 (1H, t, *J*_{ortho} 8 Hz, H-5'), 6.81 (1H, dd, *J*_{ortho} 8 Hz, *J*_{meta} 2.5 Hz), 6.74 (1H, d, *J*_{ortho} 8 Hz) and 6.69 (1H, br s, H-2', ArH), 4.34 (1H, dd, *J* 9 and 6 Hz) and 4.04 (1H, dd, *J* 9 and 6 Hz), (O- CH_2), 3.8 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 2.83 (1H, septet, *J* 7 Hz, -CH-), 2.74 (2H, m, Ar- CH_2), 2.62 (1H, dd, *J* 17.5 and 8 Hz) and 2.29 (1H, dd, *J* 17.5 and 7 Hz) (CH_2 -C=O); ^{13}C nmr (22.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 176.7 (O-C=O), 159.7 (C-3'), 139.7 (C-1'), 129.6 (C-6'), 120.8 (C-5'), 114.4 (C-4') and 111.7 (C-2') (aromatic C), 72.5 (O- CH_2), 55.0 (O- CH_3), 38.7, 36.8, 34.0 ppm.

4-[(3-Phenylmethoxy)phenylmethyl]dihydrofuran-2(3H)-one (12) :

Bromoacetal 15 : The bromoacetalization reaction of the cinnamyl alcohol **13** (414 mg, 1.72 mmol) with NBS (712 mg, 4 mmol) and ethyl vinyl ether (1 ml, 0.753 g, 10 mmol) at -78° for 2 h, as described for the bromoacetal **8**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel (10 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the bromoacetal **15** (470 mg, 80%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 3010, 1580, 1380, 1240, 1140, 1100, 1020, 760, 720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (90 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.45-6.65 (9H, m, ArH), 6.60 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, Ar- HC=CH), 6.30 (1H, t of d, *J* 16 and 7 Hz, HC=CH-CH_2), 5.06 (2H, s, Ar CH_2 -O), 4.74 (1H, t, *J* 5.4 Hz, O-CH-O), 4.31 (2H, dd, *J* 7 and 1.4 Hz, $\text{HC=CH-CH}_2\text{-O}$), 3.63 (2H, q, O- CH_2CH_3), 3.43 (2H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz, CH_2Br), 1.24 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, O- CH_2CH_3).

Acetal 16 : The radical cyclization reaction of the bromoacetal **15** (564 mg, 1.65 mmol) with $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.08 ml, 96 mg, 0.3 mmol), NaCNBH_3 (280 mg, 4.44 mmol), and AIBN (catalytic) in refluxing *t*-BuOH (10 ml) as described for the acetal **9**, followed by purification of the residue on a silica gel (20 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the acetal **16** (330 mg, 64%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 3020, 1585, 1490, 1375, 1270, 1152, 1040, 732, 693 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (270 MHz, CDCl_3 , 3 : 2 mixture of diastereomers) δ 7.75-7.32 (5H, m) and 6.7-6.9 (2H, m) (ArH), 5.14 (1H, m, O-CH-O), 5.06 and 5.08 (2H, s, Ar CH_2 -O), 3.3-4.05 (4H, m, CH_2 -O and O- CH_2CH_3), 2.6-2.8 (2H, m, Ar CH_2), 2.45 (1H, m, Ar CH_2CH), 2.2 (ddd, *J* 18.6, 12.7, and 10.5 Hz), 1.99 (dd, *J* 13 and 6.7 Hz) and 1.5-1.8 (m) (H-3), 1.22 and 1.18 (3H,

t, J 7.3 Hz, O-CH₂CH₃); ¹³C nmr (50 MHz, CDCl₃, 3 : 2 mixture of diastereomers, DEPT) δ 159.1 (C), 142.6 (C), 137.3 (C), 129.5 (CH), 128.6 (2C, CH), 128.0 (CH), 127.6 (2C, CH), 121.5 (CH), 115.6 (CH), 112.6 and 112.5 (CH), 104.5 and 104.0 (CH), 71.8 (CH₂), 70.1 (CH₂), 63.1 and 62.7 (CH₂), 40.0 (CH), 39.5 (CH₂), 38.9 and 38.8 (CH₂), 15.5 and 15.4 ppm (CH₃); m/z 312 (M⁺, 10%), 267 (70), 266 (75), 249 (50), 221 (25), 198 (50), 197 (30), 175 (25), 145 (25), 108 (40), 92 (75), 91 (100), 65 (75), HRMS : m/z for C₂₀H₂₄O₃, Found : 312.1740 (Calcd. : 312.1725).

Lactone 12 : Sonochemically accelerated Jones oxidation of the acetal 16 (150 mg, 0.48 mmol) with a freshly prepared 1.6 M Jones reagent (1 ml, 1.6 mmol) in acetone (1 ml) for 5 min as described for the lactone 10, followed by purification of the residue on a silica gel (10 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 4) as eluent furnished the lactone^{4a} 12 (100 mg, 74%), m.p. 79–80° (lit.^{4a} 79–80°); ν_{\max} (neat) 1760 (γ -lactone), 1584, 1377, 1251, 1158, 1008, 735, 693 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (270 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.3–7.7 (7H, m), 7.23 (1H, d, J_{ortho} 8 Hz), 6.87 (1H, J_{ortho} 8 Hz, J_{meta} 2.5 Hz) and 6.77 (1H, d, J_{meta} 2.5 Hz) (ArH), 5.06 (2H, s, ArCH₂-O), 4.32 (1H, dd, J 9 and 6.7 Hz) and 4.0 (1H, dd, J 9 Hz and 6 Hz) (CH₂-O), 2.84 (1H, m, ArCH₂CH), 2.74 (2H, m, ArCH₂), 2.59 (1H, dd, J 17.4 and 8 Hz) and 2.28 (1H, dd, J 17.4 and 5.4 Hz) (CH₂C=O); ¹³C nmr (22.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 176.7 (O-C=O), 159.0 (C-3'), 139.7 (C-1'), 136.7, 128.5 (2C), 127.9 and 127.4 (2C) (O-CH₂C₆H₅), 129.7 (C-5'), 121.2 (C-6'), 115.5 (C-4'), 112.8 (C-2'), 72.5 (CH₂-O), 69.9 (O-CH₂Ph), 38.8, 36.9, 34.1 ppm.

E-3-(3-Methoxyphenyl)-prop-2-en-1-yl bromoacetate (17) : A solution of the cinnamyl alcohol 7 (164 mg, 1 mmol), bromoacetyl bromide (0.1 ml, 232 mg, 1.15 mmol) and dry pyridine (1 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with ether (10 ml), washed sequentially with 0.5 N aq. HCl (10 ml), water (10 ml) and brine (10 ml), and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent followed by purification of the residue on a silica gel (10 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the bromoacetate 17 (245 mg, 86%) as a yellow oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1730 (O-C=O), 1590, 1580, 1260, 1150, 1040, 780, 680 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (90 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.3–6.6 (4H, m, ArH), 6.6 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, Ar-HC=CH), 6.2 (1H, t of d, J 16 and 6 Hz, Ar-CH=CH), 4.7 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₂-O), 3.73 (5H, s, Ar-OCH₃ and CH₂Br).

Radical cyclization reaction of the bromoacetate 17 : To a refluxing solution of the bromoacetate 17 (140 mg, 0.5 mmol) in dry benzene (10 ml), a solution of ⁿBu₃SnH (0.145 ml, 159 mg, 0.54 mmol) in dry benzene (50 ml) containing AIBN (catalytic) was added slowly over a period of 2 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for another 1 h, cooled, washed sequentially with 1% aq. ammonia (10

ml), water (10 ml) and brine (10 ml), and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the residue on a silica gel (10 g) column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the cyclized product 10 (31 mg, 30%) which was identified by comparison (tlc, ir and ¹H nmr spectra) with the sample obtained earlier. Further elution of the column with the same solvent furnished the reduced product 18 (52 mg, 51.2%) : ν_{\max} (neat) 2950, 1730 (O-C=O), 1595, 1580, 1490, 1450, 1435, 1360, 1240, 1150, 1040, 780, 685 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (80 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.6–7.3 (4H, m, ArH), 6.5 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, Ar-HC=CH), 6.15 (1H, d of t, J 16 and 6 Hz, Ar-HC=CH), 4.55 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, O-CH₂), 3.25 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 2.0 (3H, s, CH₃-C=O).

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